

Information seeking behaviour models in Information Retrieval

Information retrieval research can broadly be categorized into two streams; System centered research that focuses on the systems aspects of information retrieval including retrieval algorithms, indexing, interface design, and so on, and user-centered research that focuses on the human information behavior and user-centered or cognitive approaches to the design of information retrieval systems. Many researchers have proposed interactive models for information search and retrieval that place users in the central role of the information retrieval system. Some of the important human information and behavior models are discussed below:

- **Wilson's model-** The problem-solving model proposed by Wilson proposes that information seeking emerges as a result of an information need seen by the client who in order to fulfill that requirement, make requests upon data sources and services. This comes about within the success or failure to discover significant information. In this model, the information need of the user is the foremost vital factor in originating and driving the whole information retrieval process. In any case, agreeing to Wilson a user's information need is not a primary need but a secondary need which emerges but of needs of a more fundamental type; in order to meet these data needs the client is likely to meet diverse barriers. The essential need, which in turn creates the information need, may emerge from the role of the person in an environment, a lifestyle or a course of work. Wilson distinguishes three major types of barrier in the context of an information need: individual, role-related and environmental.

While the fundamental principle and focus remained the same, Wilson created a modern HIB model in 1996 that proposes that information-seeking behavior is a goal oriented with the resolution of the problem, and possibly the presentation of the solution, as the goal. In moving through each of the stages of issue identification, problem definition; problem resolution and solution presentation. uncertainty and instability must be diminished through the interactions of the clients with the data sources.

- **Dervin's Model-** The sense-making approach of Dervin sets that clients go through different stages in making sense of the world. The first phase sets up the context for the information need, which she calls a situation. People find a crevice between what they understand and what they need to know in order to make sense of the current circumstance. These gaps are showed by formulation of questions. Thus, according to the sense-making approach, the HIB is implemented in terms of four constituent components:

- a situation in time and space, which defines the context in which an information problem emerges.
- A gap which recognizes the difference between the contextual situation and the desired situation.
- A result which is the consequence of sense making process.
- A bridge that is the means of closing the gap between the situation and the outcome.

Marchionini suggests that the situation gap model of Brenda Dervin applies more to common human conditions than information seeking, but it has been adopted by researchers in data science and communications as a framework for studying the information-seeking process. Wilson says that the clarity of Dervin's model lies somewhat within the methodological results, since in connection to HIB, it can lead to a way of addressing that can uncover the nature of a risky circumstance, the degree to which information serves to bridge the gap of uncertainty, and the nature of the results from the use of information.

Ellis's model- According to Ellis, an information-seeking process has the mentioned stages:

- starting- starting the information-seeking process, e.g. when the client inquires a few learned colleague
- chaining- following links of citations in known material
- browsing- comprising some sort of undirected or semi-structured searching for information.
- differentiating- filtering the information received.
- monitoring- keeping track of advancements within the user's field of interest.
- extracting- selecting the relevant information from a source.
- confirming- checking the precision of information.
- finishing- conducting a final search. to complete the process. Information-seeking processes don't essentially follow these stages in strict pattern. According to Ellis, the detailed interrelation or interaction of the features in any individual information-seeking design will depend on the special circumstances of the information-seeking activities of the individual concerned at the time of looking for the information.

Bates model- The Berry-picking model of information seeking proposed by Bates recommends that as a result of reading and learning from the information retrieved through the search process, users' information needs and inquiries ceaselessly shift. The berry-picking model also demonstrates that clients' data needs are fulfilled by a series of selections and bits of information found along the

complete information search process, as opposed to the output of any particular search set.

Kulthau's model- Kulthau considered how students search for information as part of their process. Based on this, she proposed a model that involves seven stages:

Ask: initiation

Topic selection

pre-focus exploration

focus formulation

Information collection

search closure or presentation (writing).

Wilson says that Kulthau's model is simpler than Ellis's model in drawing attention with the feelings related with the various stages and activities. Based on Kulthau's model, Vakkari proposes an assignment-based model that begins with a focus. Vakkari comments that the finding of a focus which is comparable to the hypothesis in research, is significant in any search process. At the starting, that is at the pre-focus stage the search remains undirected; once the focus has been developed, the search for data becomes more directed.

- **Ingwersen's model-** Ingwersen's model proposes that information search and retrieval is characterized by:
 - a. an individual user's cognitive space, which is characterized by the work and interests of the user, the current cognitive state of the user, a problem or goal, uncertainty, and information needs and information behavior.
 - b. the social or organizational environment, which is characterized by the domain, strategies or goals of the organization, and tasks and preferences.

Wilson comments that Ingwersen's model has a close family resemblance to the models of information-seeking behavior, for example the two elements - 'user's cognitive space' and 'social organizational environment' resemble the elements of 'person in context' and 'environmental factors' in Wilson's model.

- **Belkin's model-** The episode model of Belkin centers on the activities carried out in an information search from scanning to looking inside the system of 'goal of Interaction', 'mode of retrieval' and 'resource considered'. The thought behind this model is that individuals commonly engage in different searching behaviors over a set of information retrieval sessions. According to Belkin's model any single information-seeking methodology can be portrayed according to its location within the four dimensions of 'scanning to searching', 'goal of interaction', 'mode of retrieval' and 'resource considered'.

- **Saracevic's model-** In 1996 Saracevic proposed a stratified interaction model, and he modified it in 1997. The fundamental assumption of the stratified interaction model is that clients interact with information retrieval systems in order to utilize information and the utilization of information is associated with cognition and situational application. The major components within the stratified model are clients and computers, each with a host of other variables. The interface empowers a variety of interactions to be started, which can be conceived as a arrangement of processes happening in several associated levels or strata, cache involving different elements or specific processes. Like on the human side processes may be physiological (e.g. visual, tactile or sound-related), mental and cognitive; on the computer side they may be physical and symbolic, whereas the interface provides for an interaction on the surface level.

References

- Bhattacharjee, Sudip, Bhattacharjee, Sucheta and Sinha, Manoj Kumar. (2013). Information seeking behaviour: Concept, models, case study. Germany: LAP LAMBERT Academic Publishing.
- Dervin, B. "An Overview of Sense-Making Research: Concepts, Methods, and Results to Date." Annual Meeting of the International Communication Association, Dallas Tx.(1983).
- Ellis, D., A behavioural approach to information retrieval design. Journal of Documentation, 1989. 46: 318-338.
- Godbold, Natalya "Beyond information seeking: towards a general model of information behaviour." Information Research 11.4 (2006).
- Järvelin, K. & Wilson, T.D. (2003). On conceptual models for information seeking and retrieval research. Information Research, 9(1), 163.
- Rather, Mudasir. (2017). Information Seeking Models in the Digital Age. 10.4018/978-1-5225-2255-3.ch392.
- Wilson, T.D and Walsh, C. "Information behaviour: an interdisciplinary perspective." University of Sheffield Department of Information Studies (1996).
- Wilson, T.D. (1981) On user studies and information needs. Journal of Documentation, 37, 3-15
- Wilson, T.D. "Evolution in information behaviour modeling: Wilson's model." Theories of information behavior (2007). pp. 31-36.
- Wilson, T.D. "Models in information behaviour research." Journal of Documentation 55.3 (1999): 249-270